

Can Providing Previously Reported Data on Survey and Census Web Forms Increase Response Rates?

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Abstract

The USDA's National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) has incorporated Previously Reported Data (PRD) in its 2022 US Census of Agriculture (COA) and survey programs. This paper investigates the potential use of historical PRD and its influence on response rates to the 2022 Census of Agriculture. For the study group, utilization of PRD significantly increased web response rates but not overall response rates. The findings provide evidence of PRD's capacity to positively impact response rates, potentially creating a strong foundation for long-term studies.

Key Words: *Previously reported data, Census, Response Rate, Survey*

1. Introduction

The United States Department of Agriculture's National Agricultural Statistics Service (USDA NASS) provides accurate and timely agricultural data in support of American agriculture. Established in 1863, NASS is the primary statistical agency within the USDA, and its mission is to collect, compile, and disseminate a wide range of agricultural statistics and information. These statistics are vital for farmers, policymakers, businesses, researchers, and the public to make informed decisions and understand the state of agriculture in the United States.

USDA NASS conducts more than 100 surveys and produces more than 450 reports each year on crop production, livestock, economic indicators, and other aspects of agriculture. The Census of Agriculture (COA), which is conducted every five years, provides comprehensive and up-to-date data on the agricultural sector within a country. Detailed information is published on the number and types of farms, land usage, crop production, livestock, farm management practices, and other agricultural activities. These data are valuable for monitoring trends in agriculture, identifying areas of growth or decline, and formulating agricultural policies that can better support the industry and rural communities. The COA is widely used by government agencies, policymakers, researchers, and the agricultural industry.

In preparation for the COA, the Web Only Census Content Test (Web Test) is conducted as part of census form development and testing. The census form's content and structure are evaluated and refined before deploying the census. Overall, the Web Test is an integral part of the survey development process, ensuring that the census form is well-structured, free of ambiguities, and capable of collecting high-quality data.

Response rates in censuses and surveys are one metric with broad implications for the quality and validity of the data collected. When response rates are low, nonresponse bias can be introduced, potentially leading to unreliable findings, making it difficult to draw meaningful conclusions or make informed decisions. In contrast, surveys with high response rates are more likely to yield data that is representative of the population, providing researchers and decision-makers with reliable insights.

Response rates to the COA have dwindled in recent iterations. The cause of the drop is multifaceted, but some reasons include (Bradburn, N.M. 1978, Snijkers et al. 2013, Tourangeau 2000):

1. **Complexity and Length of the Census:** If the COA becomes more complex, lengthy, or burdensome to complete, it may deter potential respondents. Farmers, and agricultural workers may perceive the COA as time-consuming, leading to a decrease in response rates.
2. **Privacy Concerns:** Concerns about the privacy and confidentiality of the data collected can be a deterrent. Respondents may be hesitant to share sensitive information about their agricultural operations due to worries about data security and potential misuse of the information.
3. **Changes in Agricultural Practices:** Shifts in the agricultural industry, such as the rise of large-scale commercial farming or changes in the types of crops and livestock produced, can affect response rates. If these shifts make respondents feel that the survey is less relevant to their operations, they may be less inclined to participate.
4. **Data Collection Methods:** The method of data collection can influence response rates. If the COA moves from in-person interviews to phone or online surveys, some respondents may be less comfortable or less likely to engage with these new methods, potentially leading to lower response rates.
5. **Socioeconomic Factors:** Economic factors, such as fluctuations in agricultural markets and farm income, can influence farmers' willingness to participate in the COA. During economically challenging times, respondents may prioritize other tasks over DOQ participation.
6. **Survey Fatigue:** Farmers and agricultural businesses may experience survey fatigue, having been repeatedly surveyed on various topics related to agriculture. The increasing number of surveys and questionnaires that they are asked to complete can lead to decreased motivation to participate in the COA, which is yet another data collection effort.

To address declining response rates, survey and census administrators often implement strategies to improve outreach, communication, and questionnaire design to make the COA more appealing and manageable for respondents. One such strategy is the use of PRD in dependent interviewing.

Using previously reported data in dependent interviewing for surveys and censuses is a strategic approach that has the potential to decrease burden (Tomaskovic-Devey et al. 1994) and increase response rates. This method involves incorporating information gathered from prior survey and census responses to enhance the efficiency of subsequent surveys and censuses (Jäckle 2006, pp. 1). By leveraging historical data, NASS can streamline the questioning process, reduce burden, and potentially improve the overall quality of the collected data.

When respondents provide information that aligns with their previous answers, the survey or census experience may be more efficient for respondents but also has the potential to enhance data accuracy, benefiting researchers and organizations that rely on NASS data.

In this study, whether there is a positive relationship between having PRD on the Web Test and the response rates to the COA is assessed. Tests of association and likelihood are evaluated, and results are discussed.

2. Methods

The data used in this paper come NASS's Web Test and the COA. Data linkage was performed to isolate all records that responded via the web to both the Web Test and the COA. The linked data set contained the following information: presence or absence of PRD on the Web Test and success of failure (1/0) for responding to the COA. Four groups were created from these data to test and explore the association between having PRD on the Web Test and responding to the Census: 1. Did not have PRD on Web Test and responded to the Census $n_1=40$ (non-PRD group), 2. Did not have PRD on the Web Test and did not respond to the Census $n_2=338$, (non-PRD group), 3. Did have PRD on Web Test and responded to the Census $n_3=175$ (PRD group), and 4. Did have PRD on Web Test and did not respond to the Census $n_4=834$ (PRD group) (see figure 1). The datasets were linked, compiled, and analyzed using SAS JMP Pro 14.

Figure 1 Illustrates the respondent relative frequency to the Census by PRD group. PRD group designation is listed on the x-axis along with level 0/1, where 0= did not respond to Census (blue bars) and 1= did respond (black bars) to Census.

2.1 Fisher's Exact Test

Fisher's Exact Tests of association are widely used to examine the association between two categorical variables, particularly when dealing with small sample sizes. This test is valuable when the assumptions of a traditional chi-squared test may not be met due to limited data. In a Fisher's exact test, the null hypothesis assumes that there is no association between the two variables, meaning that any observed differences are merely due to random chance. The test calculates the probability of obtaining a distribution of data as extreme as, or more extreme than, the observed data under this null hypothesis. If the p -value derived from the test is sufficiently low (typically less than a chosen significance level, such as 0.05), one can reject the null hypothesis, concluding that the variables are associated.

2.2 Nominal Logistic Regression: Odds Ratio

Nominal Logistic Regression is a modeling technique used when the dependent variable is categorical with two or more levels, making it an extension of binary logistic regression. This method is especially useful when the objective is to understand how predictor variables influence a multi-category outcome. Nominal logistic regression estimates coefficients for each level of the categorical outcome, allowing you the effect of predictors on the odds of belonging to one category to be compared to a reference category.

Nominal logistic regression was performed to evaluate the odds ratio for having PRD and responding to the Census. Various factors influence whether an individual responds to the COA. A known predictor of response to the COA is previous response history to surveys and censuses. To control for previous response history, the propensity score of a respondent was included as a predictor. The propensity scores are generated using previous response history and other reported data.

2.3 Bootstrap

Bootstrap sampling is a resampling technique used in statistics to estimate the sampling distribution of a statistic by repeatedly sampling from the observed data with replacement. This method is especially valuable when the underlying population distribution is unknown or when sample sizes are limited. By generating many resampled datasets, the response rate by group, the means, and a distribution of the differences were obtained.

For each bootstrap sample, the PRD/non-PRD groups were resampled 1000 times and the response rate for each bootstrap sample was recorded. Specifically, a random sample of 378 was drawn with replacement from the observed records with non-PRD, and another random sample of 1109 was drawn with replacement from the observed records with PRD. The variable of interest was response (1) or nonresponse (0). The response rate of each group was determined (number of 1s—responders—divided by the sample size). The difference in the two response rates was recorded. This process was conducted 1000 times and the distribution of the differences constructed.

3. Results

3.1 Fishers Exact Test

Fisher's Exact Test	Prob	Alternative Hypothesis
Left	0.9995	Prob(Census=1) is greater for Web Test=0 than 1
Right	0.0010	Prob(Census=1) is greater for Web Test=1 than 0
2-Tail	0.0020	Prob(Census=1) is different across Web Test

The p -value serves as an indicator of the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no significant relationship or difference between the variables under investigation. The alternative is that the response rate is greater for the PRD than the non-PRD group. The response rate of the PRD group was significantly greater than the non-PRD group for the Web COA test ($p = 0.001$).

3.2 Nominal Logistic Regression: Odds Ratios

Table 1 Odds ratio for responding to the COA (1=PRD, 0=non-PRD)

Level1	/Level2	Odds Ratio	Prob>Chisq	Lower 95%	Upper 95%
1	0	1.7754941	0.0021	1.230577	2.5617083
0	1	0.5632235	0.0021	0.3903645	0.8126269

The association between having PRD on the Web Test and responding to the COA is statistically significant (odds ratio = 1.775; $p = 0.002$).

3.3 Bootstrap

In this study, the PRD response rate was greater than the non-PRD response rate in 97.9% of the bootstrap samples (see figure 2). Therefore, the response rates of the PRD group is significantly greater than that of the non-PRD group.

Figure 2. Distribution of differences in response rate between the PRD and non-PRD group

3. Conclusion

In this study, the potential effect of the prior exposure to PRD on response rates to 2022 Census of Agriculture was explored. Using multiple methods, the response rates in the prior PRD group was consistently found to be significantly greater than those in the non-PRD group.

This research underscores the potential of PRD as a valuable tool for enhancing response rates, particularly in the realm of web-based surveys. However, the larger body of research up to this point reflects Hoogendoorn (2004) findings where overall response rates remain unchanged. The USDA's National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) is committed to improving web response rates, and PRD represents a promising avenue to achieve this objective. However, further, more in-depth, investigations are necessary to cement these findings. Future research should consider gathering data across multiple surveys leading to the COA and exploring how different levels of exposure to PRD may influence response rates.

In conclusion, the incorporation of PRD holds considerable promise for the agricultural data collection process, and this study provides a steppingstone for future endeavors in this

field. The potential benefits for both data accuracy and data collection efficiency make PRD a compelling subject for ongoing research.

4. Acknowledgements

The findings and conclusions in this article are those of the authors, have not been formally disseminated by the U.S. Department of Agriculture and should not be construed to represent any Agency determination or policy.

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